

Data for the Paper: “Impact of Data Assimilation Frequency and Observation Location in Thermal Effluent Modeling for Coastal Waters” by N. Alsulaiman, M. van Reeuwijk, and M. D. Piggott.

Temps.mat

This file contains temperature data for each simulation case. Each variable represents temperature data from 5-June-2022 to 19-June-2022, exported every 10 minutes. The data is organized such that each row corresponds to a grid cell, and each column corresponds to a time step.

Variables included:

- **Baseline_Temp:** Temperature from the Baseline Model.
- **Truth_Temp:** Temperature from the Truth Model.
- **OSSE1_P1_HT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P1, EnKF High Tide.
- **OSSE1_P1_LT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P1, EnKF Low Tide.
- **OSSE1_P1_HTLT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P1, EnKF High and Low Tides.
- **OSSE1_P1_Hour_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P1, EnKF hourly.
- **OSSE1_P1_10Mins_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P1, EnKF 10 minutes.
- **OSSE1_P2_HT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P2, EnKF High Tide.
- **OSSE1_P2_LT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P2, EnKF Low Tide.
- **OSSE1_P2_HTLT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P2, EnKF High and Low Tides.
- **OSSE1_P2_Hour_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P2, EnKF hourly.
- **OSSE1_P2_10Mins_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P2, EnKF 10 minutes.
- **OSSE1_P3_HT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P3, EnKF High Tide.
- **OSSE1_P3_LT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P3, EnKF Low Tide.
- **OSSE1_P3_HTLT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P3, EnKF High and Low Tides.
- **OSSE1_P3_Hour_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P3, EnKF hourly.
- **OSSE1_P3_10Mins_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at P3, EnKF 10 minutes.
- **OSSE1_All_HT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at all positions, EnKF High Tide.
- **OSSE1_All_LT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at all positions, EnKF Low Tide.
- **OSSE1_All_HTLT_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at all positions, EnKF High and Low Tides.
- **OSSE1_All_Hour_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at all positions, EnKF hourly.
- **OSSE1_All_10Mins_Temp:** Temperature from OSSE1 Model at all positions, EnKF 10 minutes.
- **OSSE2_Temp:** Temperature from EnKF OSSE2 Model.

selected_time.mat

This file contains time step tags corresponding to the temperature data in `Temps.mat`. It provides the specific timestamps for each column in the temperature matrices.

RMSE_Calculation.m

This script calculates the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for each simulation scenario (Baseline, OSSE1 cases, and OSSE2) compared to the Truth Model. The RMSE is calculated for each grid cell (row) across the selected time period according to Eq. 11 and 12 in the paper.

- **Outputs:**
 - `RMSEs.mat`: A MAT-file containing RMSE values for each simulation scenario.

RMSE_Baseline_Plot.m

This script plots the RMSE between the Truth Model and the Baseline Model (Eq. 11 in paper).

Error_Reduction_plots_OSSE1.m

This script calculates the error reduction achieved by the OSSE1 scenarios compared to the Baseline Model, using Eq. 13 from the paper.

Error_Reduction_OSSE2.m

This script calculates the error reduction achieved by the OSSE2 scenario compared to the Baseline Model, using Eq. 13 from the paper.

brewermap.m (Third-Party Library)

This paper uses the `brewermap` function to apply ColorBrewer colormaps in MATLAB, which are based on color specifications and designs developed by Cynthia Brewer (<https://colorbrewer2.org>)

Source: <https://uk.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/45208-colorbrewer-attractive-and-distinctive-colormaps>

Citation: Stephen23 (2024). ColorBrewer: Attractive and Distinctive Colormaps (<https://github.com/DrosteEffect/BrewerMap/releases/tag/3.2.5>), GitHub. Retrieved October 1, 2024.